

Supplementary material

Development of auxin reporters in oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*)

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Supplementary Figure S1. Hairy roots expressing the GUS reporter gene under the control of either the minimal CaMV 35S promoter or the full CaMV 35S promoter, in the absence or presence of auxin induction (1 μ M NAA).

Supplementary Figure S2. Growth of hairy roots induced by the C58C1 or K599 *Agrobacterium* strains.

Supplementary Figure S3. Promoter fragments of *BnaIAA* genes used in the BIP3 reporter construct.

Supplementary Figure S4. Histochemical GUS staining of different tissues of *B. napus* transgenic plants.

Supplementary Figure S5. Histochemical GUS staining of *B. napus* flowers expressing DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω) or BIP3-GUS (+/- Ω).

Supplementary Figure S6. The DR5cc- Ω reporter is auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots.

Supplementary Figure S7. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 1).

Supplementary Figure S8. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -VENUS (Line 2).

Supplementary Figure S9. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 2).

Supplementary Figure S10. Cytokinin and auxin reporter activity in *B. napus* hairy roots, transgenic Line 2.

Supplementary Figure S11. *BnaIAA* genes selected for qDII reporter construction.

Supplementary Figure S12. qDII reporters are auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots.

Supplementary Figure S13. Stability of the TagBFP fluorescence in qDII constructs.

Supplementary Figure S14. Schematic representation of the constructs prepared for this study.

Supplementary Figure S15. Sequence alignment of the two *ACC* gene copies in *B. napus* DH12075.

Supplementary Table S1. List of oligonucleotides.

Supplementary Figure S1. Hairy roots expressing the GUS reporter gene under the control of either the minimal CaMV 35S promoter or the full CaMV 35S promoter, in the absence or presence of auxin induction (1 μ M NAA). Scale bars represent 500 μ m.

A

Supplementary Figure S2. Growth of hairy roots induced by the C58C1 or K599 *Agrobacterium* strains. **(A)** Relative root length (% of the initial root length at day 0) was measured after 8 and 16 days of culture in four lines transformed by C58C1 and four lines transformed by K599. Three independent biological replicates were performed, and the data are presented as mean values with standard deviation. **(B)** Representative images of hairy root lines at the initial time point and after 8 days of culture. Scale bar represents 1 mm.

pBnaIAA1

BnaC08g09640D AAAGTAACGCGTCCAAATATCTCAG TGTCCC ATCTT TGTCCC CTTGCCTCTC
BnaA08g30190D AAAGTAACGCGTCCAAATATCTCAG TGTCCC ATCTT TGTCCC CTTGCCTCTC

pBnaIAA2

BnaA05g16700D ACGAGTCCACATGGGCGGCCATAGCGTTTGTGTCCTACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC
BnaC05g29330D TCGAGTCCACATGGGCGGCCATAGCGTTTGTGTCCTACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC
BnaA01g24190D TCGAGTCCACATGGGCGGCCATAGCGTTTGTG TGTCCC ACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC
BnaC01g31190D TCGAGTCCACATGGGCGGCCATAGCGTTTGTG TGTCCC ACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC
BnaA03g36940D TCGAGTTCACATGGACGGCCAAAGCGTTTA TGTCCC ACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC
BnaC03g43120D TCGAGTTCACATGGACGGCCAAAGCGTTTA TGTCCC ACCTT TGTCCC CTTGC

pBnaIAA4

BnaA09g16590D TTTGGCTATAGATGAAAG TGTCCC ACGAA TGTCCC CAAAATGAT GGGACAC
BnaCnng63870D TTTGGCTATAGATGAAAG TGTCCC ACGAA TGTCCC CAAAATGAT GGGACAC

Supplementary Figure S3. Promoter fragments of *BnaIAA* genes used in the BIP3 reporter construct. AuxRE motifs in the forward orientation (TGTCCC) are indicated by green boxes, whereas AuxRE motifs in the reverse orientation (GGGACA) are indicated by blue boxes.

Supplementary Figure S4. Histochemical GUS staining of different tissues of *B. napus* transgenic plants. Independent transgenic lines from (A) DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω) and (B) BIP3-GUS (+/- Ω) are presented. Scale bars represent 2 mm (seedlings, flowers), 200 μm (root tips), and 500 μm (embryos).

Supplementary Figure S5. Histochemical GUS staining of *B. napus* flowers expressing DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω) or BIP3-GUS (+/- Ω). Flowers were sprayed with water (Mock) or 50 μ M NAA in water, and stained after 24 h. Scale bars represent 2 mm.

Supplementary Figure S6. The DR5cc reporter is auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots. **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips from independent lines expressing DR5cc-Ω-VENUS or DR5cc-Ω-mCherry treated with mock or 1 μM NAA, and imaged after 6 or 24 h. Scale bars represent 40 μm. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS and mCherry fluorescence intensities in mock- and NAA-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values are normalized to the corresponding mock.

Supplementary Figure S7. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 1). Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock and abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scale bars represent 40 μ m. Quantification is shown in Figure 4.

Supplementary Figure S8. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -VENUS (Line 2). **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock and abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scale bars represent 40 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS fluorescence intensity in mock- and stress-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); ** P < 0.01; *** P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values are normalized to the corresponding mock.

Supplementary Figure S9. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 2). **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock and abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scale bars represent 40 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative mCherry fluorescence intensity in mock- and stress-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values are normalized to the corresponding mock.

A

Supplementary Figure S10. Cytokinin and auxin reporter activity in *B. napus* hairy roots, transgenic Line 2. **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of hairy roots co-expressing TCSv2-VENUS and DR5cc-Q-mCherry treated with mock, NAA (1 μ M, 24 h), and/or BAP (5 μ M, 2 h). Images are shown as VENUS (top row), mCherry (middle row) and merged channels (bottom row: magenta color for DR5cc-Q-mCherry and yellow for TCSv2-VENUS). Scale bars represent 20 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS (left) and mCherry (right) fluorescence intensities in mock- and hormone-treated hairy roots. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each channel, values are normalized to the corresponding mock.

A

atggcttacgagaaagtcaatgagcttaaccttaaggacacagagcttcgtcttgatta
M A Y E K V N E L N L K D T E L R L G L
cccgaacggagcaagataaggaagaacaagagggttcttgcgttagaagcaacaagcgt
P G T E Q D K E E Q E V S C V R S N **K R**
caactacagagcgataacgaggaagaatctacacttcctacgaaaactcaaactcgttggt
Q L Q S D N E E E S T L P T K T Q I **V G**
tggcctccgggtgagatcttaccgtaaaaaacaacaacagtggtgagctatgtgaaagtgagt
W P P V R S Y R **K N N N S V S** Y V K V S
atggatggagctccataccttaggaaaatagatctcaagacatacaaaaactatccagag
M D G A P Y L R K I D L K T Y K N Y P E
cttctcaaggcattagagaacctgttcaagttcacgatcgggtgaatacaacgaaagagaa
L L K A L E N L F K F T I G E Y N E R E
ggatacaaaaggatctggagttgtaccaacgtacgaggataaagatggagattggatggtg
G Y K G S G V V P T Y E D K D G D W M L
gttggtgatgttccatgggatatgttctcttctcttgaagagactcaggatcatgaaa
V G D V P W D M F S S S C K R L R I M K
ggatctgatgctcttgctttggactcggccttatga
G S D A L A L D S A L *

B

atgatgggcagtggttgggctgaatctgagggagactgagctgtgtcttggctcttcccgg
M M G S V G L N L R E T E L C L G L P G
ggtgatacggcgctccccgttgactggaaccaagagaggattctcagagacggttgatctg
G D T A S P L T G T **K R** G F S E T V D L
aagctgaatctgaacaatgaacctgaaagcaaggaaggatctaagagccacgacgctcgtg
K L N L N N E P E S K E G S K S H D V V
agtgctatttccaaggaaaagagttcatgtaccaagatccaaccaagcctcctgccaag
S A I S K E K S S C T K D P T K P P A K
gcacaagttgtgggatggccaccgggtgagatcataccggaagaacgtgatgggttcatgc
A Q V **V G W P P V R S Y R** **K N V M G S C**
caaaaatcaagcagtagcgcggacacggcggttgtgaaggtgtcgtatggacggagca
Q K S S S S A D T A A F V K V S M D G A
ccgtacttgaggaaaatcgacttgaagatgtataagagctacgacgaactctctgacgct
P Y L R K I D L K M Y K S Y D E L S D A
ttgtccaacatgttccagctcttttaccatgggaaaaaatggaggagaagaaggaatgata
L S N M F S S F T M G K N G G E E G M I
gacttcatgaatgagaggaaagtaatggatacagtgagttagttgggactatgttccctct
D F M N E R K V M D T V S S W D Y V P S
tatgaagacaaagacgggtgattggatgctcgtcggcgacgtcccttgccaatgttcggt
Y E D K D G D W M L V G D V P W P M F V
gatacatgcaagcgtttacgtctcatgaaggatctgacgccattggtctcgtccttaga
D T C K R L R L M K G S D A I G L A P R
gcaatggagaagtgcaagagtagagcttga
A M E K C K S R A *

Supplementary Figure S11. *BnaIAA* genes selected for qDII reporter construction. The coding regions of *BnaA01g24190D* (**A**; IAA2) and *BnaA08g27770D* (**B**; IAA17), together with their corresponding amino acid sequences, are shown. KR motif is highlighted in green, the degron motif in yellow, and the degron tail in blue.

Supplementary Figure S12. qDII reporters are auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots. (A, B) IAA2 Line 2 and (C, D) IAA17 Line 2 showing representative epidermal cell images under mock and NAA (10 μ M, 2 h) conditions, with TagBFP (left) and VENUS (right) channels, and corresponding VENUS/TagBFP fluorescence intensity quantifications. Values are normalized to the corresponding mock. Scale bars represent 20 μ m. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Welch's t-test.

Supplementary Figure S13. Stability of the TagBFP fluorescence in qDII constructs. Quantification of relative TagBFP fluorescence intensity in independent hairy root lines expressing qDII-IAA2 / IAA17 treated with mock or NAA (10 μ M, 2 h). Error bars indicate SD. No significant differences were observed in treated samples compared with the mock control (Welch's t-test).

DR5cc-GUS

DR5cc-Ω-GUS

DR5cc-Ω-Venus

DR5cc-Ω-mCherry

BIP3-GUS

BIP3-Ω-GUS

IAA2/IAA17-qDII

Supplementary Figure S14. Schematic representation of the constructs prepared for this study. Addgene plasmids used for MoClo cloning are indicated.

Supplementary Table S1. List of oligonucleotides.

Genotyping of T1 plants

GUS_F	TGCTCTACACCACGCCGAACA
GUS_R	GAGCATCTCTTCAGCGTAAGGG
TL_rolA_F	GTTAGGCGTGCAAAGGCCAAG
TL_rolA_R	TGCGTATTAATCCCGTAGGTC
TR_aux1_F	CATAGGATCGCCTCACAGGT
TR_aux1_R	CGTTGCTTGATGTCAGGAGA

Transgene copy number assessment

ACC_amp_F	ATCGCTGGAGTTTCTGCCGAA
ACC_amp_R	CAGATGCCATTGACGATCTCTTGTAG
Q_ACC-A_F	GTGAGCTGTATAATCGAGCGA
Q_ACC-A_R	GCATCGGCTCTTCTGCATAG
Q_ACC-A_probe	AGGACGAACACCTATTAGACATTCGTTCCATT
Q_GUS_F	GACGAAAACGGCAAGAAAAAGCAG
Q_GUS_R	TGAAGTACCTGCCAGTCAACAG
Q_GUS_probe	AATGCTCTACACCACGCCGAACACCTG